

Data Operational Driven AI-based Architecture for Natural Disaster Management

Serena Sebbio*, Lorenzo Carnevale*, Daniel Balouek[†], Antonino Galletta*, Manish Parashar[‡], Massimo Villari*

*Department of Mathematics, Physics, Informatic and Earth Science, University of Messina,

Messina Via Stagno D'Alcontres 98166, Italy

{sersebbio, lcarnevale, angalletta, mvillari}@unime.it

[†]IMT Atlantique, Nantes Université, École Centrale Nantes

CNRS, Inria, LS2N, UMR 6004, F-44000 Nantes, France

daniel.balouek@inria.fr

[‡]Scientific Computing and Imaging Institute, University of Utah, USA

manish.parashar@utah.edu

Abstract—Natural disasters pose increasing threats to communities and economies worldwide, emphasizing the urgency for technological interventions to support first responders and decision-makers in affected areas. To address this need, we introduce a novel computing continuum architecture designed for efficient offloading of distributed intelligences across cloud, edge, and deep edge tiers. Our approach leverages an AI cross-layer framework, integrating service, network, and infrastructure management, to optimize decision-making processes in time-sensitive disaster scenarios. By employing federated learning techniques, our architecture enables both mobile and stationary devices to autonomously train local models, contributing to the development of a comprehensive global common model. Through this collaborative approach, we aim to enhance the capabilities of disaster management systems, facilitating more effective responses to critical events

Index Terms—Natural Disaster Management, Artificial Intelligence, Computing Continuum, Federated Learning, Software Architecture, Operational Data

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, we have assisted in the rise of the number of natural disasters all around the world. In this regard, the Institute for Economics and Peace [1] captured data between the 1900 and 2019, revealing an increase from 39 incidents in 1960 to 396 in 2019. The largest amount of natural disasters was experienced in 2005, where 90000 people died after 442 incidents and another 160 million people were in need of immediate assistance. As if that was not enough, natural disasters represent an issue also for the economies of countries. Once again, the Institute for Economics and Peace reported that the resulting cost of addressing damage caused by natural disasters has risen from US\$ 50 billion per year in the 1980s to US\$ 200 billion per year in the last decade. There is, therefore, the need for interventions aimed at preserving the fragility of lands and supporting the first responders as soon as the disaster happens, as well as during the following hours.

Although some software architectures have been proposed for facing the needs that climate change (e.g., flood, wildfire, tornado, tsunami, earthquake) pointed out, only a few are the solutions that involve distributed artificial intelligence and even

fewer are the solutions that involve the computing continuum. The main goal of such architectures is improving the natural disaster management (NDM) by accelerating extreme data analytics algorithms, emergency phenomenon modeling, evolution predictions, simulation and interactive visualization, by increasing trustworthiness, accuracy and responsiveness.

In a software architecture, the business or domain layer is where the application's business logic operates. Specifically, the business logic is a collection of rules that tell the system how to run one or more applications, based on the organization's guidelines. This essentially determines the behavior of the entire application. After one action finishes, it tells the application what to do next. In this regard, operational data points out how data generated by business operations, which are typically used to monitor and manage day-to-day operations, make decisions about resource allocation, and improve business processes. In other words, operational data try to monitor the behavior of the system itself. This is because such data provide insights into how components interact with the business, and what services they are more useful for a specific context.

In this paper, we propose a novel software architecture for facing the above-mentioned issues. The architecture aims at integrating the capacity of the computing continuum paradigm of distributing computation near the data source with the need of running artificial intelligence model in devices deployed in remote and hard accessible areas. The architecture aims to achieve a certain level of autonomy on decision-making about, e.g., resource allocation, task scheduling, load balancing and task offloading. For this purpose, the software architecture exploits operational data on all layers with the intent to predict configuration files that drive the evolution of the whole system. This is achievable by designing a cross-layer decision-making framework.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The motivation why building a new software architecture for achieving the above-mentioned needs is described in Section II. Related works are, instead, reported in Section III, while an overview of the architecture is available in Section IV. The application

of the proposed architecture in a NDM scenario and a critical discussion about the future challenges are reported in V. Conclusion remarks and future research activities are, finally, discussed in Section VI.

II. MOTIVATION

In the current climate change era, the NDM is becoming crucial at global level for addressing the new challenges that are appearing in Nature. Indeed, first responders are in urgent need of technological support. In this regard, the Trusted Extremely Precise Mapping and Prediction for Emergency Management (TEMA) is a Horizon Europe project which aims to improve NDM systems [2].

According to the TEMA end users requirements, a pool of needs have been highlighted, such as (a) the ability to collect and share crucial information, (b) the lack of an enhanced sharing information tool, (c) the fusion of many heterogeneous extreme data sources and (d) advanced and interactive visualization systems, combining data fusion capabilities for enabling critical real-time decision support features. On the other hand, a natural disaster scenario is typically characterized by energy- and Internet-disconnected areas, where battery-powered devices (e.g., drones, weather stations) are used for supporting first responders (e.g., civil protection, firefighters) during the exploration and rescue missions. At the same time, a coordination center monitors the operations from remote, often facing the issue of transmitting data over a satellite network, which increases the latency and reduces the possibility to make decisions in real-time. Our solution meets those requirements, by developing a cloud-edge intelligence platform. Furthermore, the management of NDM tasks in the aforementioned scenario is facilitated by pipelines that handle data in near real-time across various devices, libraries, and end-user entry points. Balancing local data collection and aggregation decisions with global optimizations that incorporate learning for system operations necessitates a software architecture that operates both horizontally to distribute data processing across the Computing Continuum and vertically by utilizing Artificial Intelligence capabilities for cross-optimizations between the infrastructure and application services. The following technical requirements must be integrated to achieve a cohesive vision of NDM:

- **Integrating learning for local decisions and global optimizations** for gaining insights and knowledge of processes while reconfiguring applications under new events or constraints.
- **Support geographically distributed deployment and device mobility** to handle dynamically different sizes of systems and fragmented applications.

III. STATE OF THE ART

The Internet of Things (IoT) is commonly linked with utilizing Machine Learning algorithms to analyze data, derive insights, and predict patterns future occurrences [3]–[5]. The progressive convergence of cloud computing and IoT devices

is resulting in the computing continuum [6]–[8]. The concept of edge computing first became to represent a middle layer, where data and computation were migrated in runtime, and later was fused with the IoT devices, because these increasingly acquired computational capacity. In the context of natural disasters, selected scientific works are available in literature to leverage the Computing Continuum for natural disasters. Løvholt et al. proposed a prototype for utilizing real-time seismic parameters and HPC in tsunami early warning and rapid post disaster assessments, faster than the physical propagation time of a tsunami [9]. Balouek et al. has proposed a solution for harnessing the computing continuum for urgent science. An Early Earthquake Warning (EEW) workflow was used as a driver for proposing a system stack that can enable the fluid integration of distributed analytics across a dynamic infrastructure spanning the computing continuum [10]. They extend this work to introduced a hierarchical approach for modeling distributed stream-based applications on a large set of heterogeneous data processing and management frameworks across the network. [11]. Babu et al. focused on using IoT home units to design a Flood and earthquake Observatory System. Results presented encouraging performance, along with the integration of solar energy for emergency situations [12]. Balouek et al. discussed research directions for tackling a fire science scenario that includes sensors at the edge of the network for smoke detection, and computational models launched in the cloud for wildfire simulation and air quality assessment [13].

The proposed software architecture differs from the ones discussed in this Section because of the exploiting of operational data. The intent is re-configuring the system in runtime by building configuration according to the monitor of resources and running services. Moreover, even though we will discuss the TEMA case study in the Section V, the architecture is general-purpose and usable on many NDM scenarios.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

In the following, we describe a software architecture designed to distribute data processing across the Computing Continuum by leveraging Artificial Intelligence capabilities. The architecture meets the requirements described in Section II.

A. Cloud-Edge-Deep Edge Tiers

Figure 1 depicts the interactions over the Computing Continuum, composed of two edge tiers and one cloud tier. In this scenario, the first edge tier, named Deep Edge, consists of autonomous and/or mobile devices for data collection and local inference of machine learning models. The need for two different edge tiers is due to the computational capacity of mobile devices. While these are commonly identified as IoT (e.g., Raspberry Pi, Jetson Nano), they are capable of serious computation. Nowadays, these devices can be considered something more than IoT. The second Edge tier comprises one or more base stations, such as small portable computers or data centers, for communication with mobile devices (e.g.,

unmanned aerial vehicles) via wireless telemetry and powerful computation. Finally, the Cloud tier provides remote support and resources for massive computation requirements.

Fig. 1. The Cloud-Edge-Deep Edge tiers are thought to distribute the computation at different distances from the data source. The offloading may happen by following a horizontal or vertical logic.

Computation is provided by computational units (e.g., agents), ranging from resource-constrained devices to powerful computers, according to the layer where they are deployed. Tasks are executed by these computational units, following the rule of deep edge-to-edge-to-cloud computing offloading to optimize resource utilization. The intent is firstly running the tasks on the lower tiers, decentralizing the computation at the Deep Edge. The offloading must be a necessity due to resource constrains (e.g., battery power, limited resources, malfunction or failure).

B. The AI Cross-Layer

Before of having a general view on the proposed software architecture, it is important to mention the core of the framework. It is represented by the cross-layer artificial intelligence. It has components, namely Operation Manager, that handle the data processing and exchanging among the logical domains. Within the AI cross-layer, there is no hierarchy between Operation Managers who are directly connected to each other, as shown in the Figure 2. Even though the Operation Managers are, therefore, located within layers, their organization is circular. Each Operation Manager can contribute to the evolution of another or the whole system.

By establishing bidirectional communication and information exchange among these machine learning models, natural disaster management systems can achieve tighter integration and coordination across the service, network and infrastructure layers and the AI capabilities, leading to more efficient resource utilization, improved application performance and enhanced overall architecture reliability and scalability. This collaborative approach facilitates adaptive decision-making and optimization across the entire stack, resulting in a more responsive and resilient computing environment. This framework enables adaptive decision-making, real-time responsive-

Fig. 2. The AI Operation Managers are cross-layers components that interact with each other for evolving the architecture behavior as if it is a complex system.

ness and efficient resource utilization in dynamic computing environments.

A Layer Operation manager is defined for each logical layer to which it provides a configuration file which is produced taking into consideration the information received from the operation managers of the other layers. An Operation Manager leverages, e.g., Reinforcement Learning techniques, where an agent learns to make sequential decisions to maximize some notion of cumulative reward.

C. The Overall Architecture

For each tier, a layered architecture is defined which is illustrated in the figure 3 and described below.

In such architecture, each layer includes a monitor that provides a diagnosis of the layer state, which is one of the inputs of the AI-based layer Operation Manager, and a layer manager that takes as input a configuration file coming out from the AI-based layer Operation Manager. Therefore, as in a loop, the Operation Manager acquires information from the monitor and affects the layer manager decision. Indeed, the output of the Operation Manager is a configuration file, which may change the behavior of the whole system. In other words, this could be seen as the sequence of decisions made by the agent. This approach requires environment modeling, action space definition, reward design (this could be based on KPIs) and policy learning to generate the configuration file: as the agent learns to make better decisions over time, it can generate a configuration file based on its learned policy. This file specifies the desired state of the layer. Therefore, the generated configuration file can then be deployed to the layer management system, which orchestrates the provisioning and configuration of resources according to the specified settings. By using, reinforcement learning, the management of the

Fig. 3. The overall architecture. Layers are affected by operational data that come from the same or another layer. The circular organization of the AI cross-layer points out the attention on a not hierarchical structure.

resources dynamically adapts to changing workload demands, resource availability, and performance requirements. The output configuration file serves as a blueprint for configuring the infrastructure according to the learned policy, enabling efficient and adaptive resource allocation in real time. Interactions between AI components targeting different layers of the system - namely, the service, network and infrastructure layers — are pivotal for achieving optimal performance, resource utilization and responsiveness.

Along with the local interfaces, the Edge and Cloud tiers feature interfaces to global AI cross-layers. These are the interfaces of other devices or, more specifically, computational units (e.g., agents) deployed in the Edge or Cloud tiers. As a consequence, agents in these two layers collaborate for making decisions based on the consensus of two or more devices, affecting not only the agent itself but also the ones in the neighbouring. The infrastructure is, therefore, configured and optimized according to both local and global actions.

D. Layer Operation Managers Interactions

In the following section, we describe how these elements could interact by exchanging information about each other's layers:

Service Operation Manager receives input about the state of the Service layer, including service performance metrics, user behavior data, and workload characteristics. It generates output in the form of configurations or optimization recommendations tailored to enhance performance, scalability, or user experience. This machine learning model also interacts with the Network Operation Manager by providing insights about service-level objectives, such as latency constraints, and receives feedback from the Network Operation Manager

regarding network conditions and bandwidth availability. By understanding the capabilities and limitations of the underlying infrastructure, the Service Operation Manager can adapt its decision-making processes and optimization strategies to ensure alignment with the available resources and infrastructure constraints.

Network Operation Manager receives input about the state of the Network layer, including network topology, latency measurements, and congestion levels. It produces output in the form of a configuration file to optimize network performance, reliability, and efficiency. Furthermore, this machine learning model interacts with both the Service and Infrastructure Layers. It communicates network-related insights and recommendations to the Service Layer, such as suggestions for optimizing data transfer protocols, and also collaborates with the Infrastructure Layer model to coordinate network resource provisioning based on service-level demands and infrastructure constraints.

Infrastructure Operation Manager is a Reinforcement Learning model that receives input about the state of the underlying infrastructure, such as server capacities, resource utilization, hardware health, and energy consumption. It generates output in the form of configurations or resource allocation strategies to optimize infrastructure performance, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. Additionally, the Infrastructure Layer model provides insights and recommendations to the Application Layer regarding infrastructure-related considerations, such as server provisioning or container orchestration, and collaborates with the Network Operation Manager model to ensure alignment between network resource provisioning and infrastructure capacity planning. The Infrastructure Operation Manager utilizes information about the Service Layer

to optimize resource provisioning, capacity planning, and infrastructure configurations to meet the specific needs of the applications running on the system.

V. USE CASE AND DISCUSSION

In the context of Natural Disaster Management (NDM), the deployment of an AI cross-layer offers a versatile framework for facilitating the deployment of edge devices, particularly drones equipped with sensors for real-time fire detection and monitoring, crucial in wildfire-prone regions. Leveraging an AI cross-layer can significantly enhance the coordination, data exchange, and decision-making processes across different layers of the architecture.

A. Natural Disaster Use Case

Here, we present a use case scenario demonstrating the application of this architecture in the context of natural disaster management, focusing on the deployment of edge devices. Consider a scenario where a region is prone to wildfires, and authorities aim to deploy a network of drones equipped with advanced sensors to detect and monitor fire outbreaks in real time. The drones operate as edge devices, collecting data from their surroundings and transmitting it to the Edge and Cloud infrastructure for analysis and decision-making.

The AI manager responsible for the infrastructure layer evaluates factors such as energy availability and response time requirements to optimize drone deployment, dynamically scaling the number of deployed drones based on environmental conditions and operational demand to ensure optimal resource allocation and scalability based on real-time demands and available energy resources. In the context of natural disaster management, the manager must consider trade-offs between energy consumption and performance to maximize the effectiveness of the deployed drones. This adaptive approach, based on the concept of cross-layer, allows for the optimization of power and performance, as discussed by Gamell et al. [14].

The network layer facilitates communication between edge devices and other components of the infrastructure. The AI manager of the network layer monitors network conditions and adapts communication protocols and routing strategies to prioritize critical data during emergencies, ensuring timely and reliable information exchange, essential for effective disaster response.

The service layer encompasses the applications and services deployed on the infrastructure to support fire detection and monitoring. The AI manager of the service layer ensures that the application meets the required Quality of Service (QoS) standards while optimizing resource utilization and prioritizing critical tasks, based on available resources and environmental conditions. This adaptive approach is adopted to maintain Quality of Service (QoS) standards while dynamically allocating resources.

Collaborative efforts between the service and network layers optimize bandwidth utilization and minimize data transmission delays, ensuring the timely delivery of critical information for analysis and decision-making. The AI manager at the

service layer collaborates with the network layer to optimize bandwidth utilization and minimize data transmission delays. It employs data compression techniques, prioritization algorithms, and adaptive data sampling strategies to ensure the timely delivery of critical information to the servers for analysis and decision-making. Additionally, it's important to note that due to the absence of a hierarchy among the operation managers of the cross-layer architecture, the adaptive approach is both top-down, ensuring the functionality of application deployment, and bottom-up, as information from lower layers influences the decision-making process in upper layers.

By leveraging advanced technologies and intelligent AI managers across different layers, organizations can improve resilience and responsiveness in addressing natural disasters, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of emergency management efforts.

B. Achievements and Challenges

In examining the potential application of an AI cross-layer in Natural Disaster Management (NDM), it becomes evident that several noteworthy achievements have been proposed alongside persistent challenges that require attention.

1) *Achievements*: The proposition of an AI cross-layer architecture holds promise in improving coordination among the various stakeholders involved in disaster response and mitigation within NDM. The integration of edge devices like drones with sensors and a cloud-edge intelligence platform is envisioned to enable real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis, potentially facilitating timely decision-making during emergencies. Additionally, the conceptualization of adaptive resource allocation strategies aims to optimize performance while considering energy constraints, potentially enhancing the effectiveness of deployed resources. Addressing critical needs in NDM, such as efficient information sharing and interactive visualization for decision support, underscores the potential progress that could be made in enhancing overall response capabilities.

2) *Challenges*: Despite the proposed advancements, challenges are anticipated. The complexity inherent in implementing and managing an AI cross-layer architecture would require robust management and coordination mechanisms to navigate effectively. Ensuring scalability to handle larger-scale disaster scenarios remains a challenge, necessitating ongoing research and development efforts to accommodate evolving technological advancements and increasing demands. Furthermore, safeguarding sensitive data exchanged across layers from potential cyber threats is anticipated to pose a significant challenge, highlighting the need for robust cross-layer security mechanisms to ensure data integrity and confidentiality. Additionally, validating the effectiveness of the proposed framework in real-world disaster management scenarios and fostering its adoption by relevant stakeholders would represent ongoing challenges requiring collaboration and cooperation across various domains.

In summary, while significant strides have been made in conceptualizing the application of AI cross-layer architecture

for NDM, addressing these challenges is imperative for realizing its potential in enhancing disaster response and mitigation efforts.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of a software architecture equipped with an AI cross layer in Natural Disaster Management (NDM) presents a promising approach for addressing critical challenges in disaster response and mitigation. By leveraging advanced technologies and intelligent AI Operation managers across different layers, our proposed solution enhances coordination, efficiency, and adaptability in managing natural disasters.

The deployment of edge devices, such as drones equipped with sensors, coupled with a cloud-edge intelligence platform, facilitates real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis, essential for timely decision-making during emergencies. The integration of adaptive resource allocation strategies ensures optimal performance while considering energy constraints inherent in battery-powered devices.

Moreover, our solution addresses key needs in NDM, including efficient information sharing, data fusion from heterogeneous sources, and interactive visualization for decision support. By providing near real-time data processing capabilities and enabling cross-layer optimizations, our architecture enhances the resilience and effectiveness of disaster management systems.

As for future work, further exploration could involve the development of more detailed design specifications using Unified Modeling Language (UML), facilitating comprehensive system modeling and refinement. Additionally, ongoing research could focus on enhancing the scalability and robustness of the proposed architecture to handle larger-scale disaster scenarios and accommodate evolving technological advancements. Implementing the proposed framework would also be a crucial future step to validate its effectiveness in real-world disaster management scenarios.

Overall, our study underscores the importance of adopting innovative approaches in disaster management, leveraging data operational driven AI based architectures to improve responsiveness and ultimately mitigate the impact of natural disasters on communities and infrastructure.

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